

Removal of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions by aluminium oxide and the prepared aluminium oxide nanoparticles

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Abstract:

Aluminium oxide (Al₂O₃) is one of the most versatile ceramic oxides. In this study, aluminium oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel assisted auto-combustion method and were characterized by using TG-DTA, XRD, FT IR and FE-SEM techniques. The resulted γ -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were used to remove of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions from model solution and contaminants in wastewater at different contact time and dosage. Then the concentration of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions in the solution after adsorption were determined by atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). These observations clearly indicated that the removal of metal ions purely depends on the amount of adsorbent and contact time. The comparison of adsorption properties of Al₂O₃ and prepared γ -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were studied. Al₂O₃ and the prepared Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were compared in removal of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions under identical conditions from wastewater, 96.31 % for Cd²⁺ ion and 56.81% for Pb²⁺ ion were removed by Al₂O₃. The prepared γ -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles can completely remove Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions contaminants in 100 mL wastewater. Therefore, the prepared γ -Al₂O₃ nanoparticles were more powerful than Al₂O₃.

1. Introduction

Nano is one billionth of a meter. In Greek, nano means dwarf. Particles of dimension of about 1 to 100 nanometers are treated as particles. Nanotechnology is the application of scientific knowledge for the purpose of producing such particle and system using them.¹ Nano-alumina is one of the most important and extensively explored ceramic materials widely used as catalysts or catalyst supports for chemical reactions, electrical insulators, structural composites for spacecraft, abrasive and thermal wear coatings, membrane applications as well as adsorbent for water and wastewater treatment.²

2. Materials and Methods

All the chemicals used were obtained from reagent (BDH). The apparatus used consist of TG-DTA (Rigaku Thermoplus TG 8120), XRD (Regaku, D/max 2200, Japan), FT IR (Perkin-Elmer (Spectrum GX) fourier transform infrared spectrophotometer), FE-SEM (EVO 60, Brand: Cards ZEISS, Germany) and AAS (Perkin-Elmer Analyst 800). Aluminium oxide nanoparticles were prepared by sol-gel synthesis using aluminium nitrate and citric acid in alkaline solution. Figure 1 show flow chart for sol-gel assisted auto-combustion synthesis of Al₂O₃ particles.

Figure 1. Flow chart for sol-gel assisted auto-combustion synthesis of Al_2O_3 particles

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 TG-DTA thermogram of Al_2O_3 gel

Figure 2 shows TG-DTA thermogram of alumina gel. Table 1 show TG-DTA data of alumina gel.

Figure 2. TG-DTA thermogram of alumina gel

Table 1. TG-DTA data of alumina gel

Temperature Range (°C)	Weight loss(%)	TGA Remark	DTA Remark
29.86– 225.13 99 °C	17.22	Dehydration	Endo peak related to loss of hydrated water and solvent
225.13– 597.73 273 °C	71.30	Decomposition	Exo peak related to decomposition of organic matter
29.86– 596.88 385 °C	88.52	Combustion	Exo peak due to combustion of residual organic matter

3.2 XRD studies on calcinated products of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles

Figure 3 shows changes of XRD patterns of alumina with different calcination temperatures. According to XRD data, phase changes were observed in alumina products calcinated at different temperatures. Up to 800°C, the alumina was amorphous nature. After calcination at 900 °C, $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase was appeared. After calcination at 1000 and 1100 °C, the peaks related to $\gamma\text{-Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase are become smaller. After calcination at 1150°C, the residual $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase is completely disappeared and pure $\alpha\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ phase was obtained. XRD data of the $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were showed characteristic peaks related to miller indices of 111, 311, 222, 400, 331, 422, 511 and 440, these peaks are well matched with standard library data of (JCPDS 79-1558 > Al_2O_3). By using Scherrer equation, crystalline sizes of the Al_2O_3 nanoparticles obtained at calcination temperature of 900, 1000, 1100 and 1150 °C were 35.15, 37.52, 45.77 and 48.10 nm, respectively. Therefore crystalline size increased with calcination temperature.

Figure 3. Changes of XRD patterns of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles with different calcinations temperatures

3.3 FTIR spectrum of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles

In this Figure 4 shows FT IR spectrum of Al_2O_3 nanoparticle obtained after calcinations at 900°C . FT IR data of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles was clearly indicated the presence of strong peaks at 594 , 462 and 432 cm^{-1} . These peaks were related with symmetric and asymmetric vibration of Al-O bond in Al_2O_3 nanoparticle.

Figure 4. FTIR spectrum of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles ($400\text{-}2000\text{ cm}^{-1}$) calcinated at 900°C

3.4 FE-SEM microphotograph of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

Figure 5 shows FE-SEM microphotograph of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. In FE-SEM microphotograph, flake-like structures of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles were observed.

Figure 5. FE-SEM microphotograph of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles calcinated at 900°C

3.5 Effect of contact time on adsorption of cadmium ion

Nanoalumina has several crystalline form and mainly used as γ -alumina form. γ - Al_2O_3 nanoparticles is a suitable material as an adsorbent because of its large specific surface area, high adsorption capacity, mechanical strength, and low-temperature modification. In this research, adsorption of cadmium ion on aluminium oxide nanoparticles was studied using 10 ppm model cadmium sulphate solution at different contact time. The changes of removal percent of cadmium were shown in Table 2. From these observations, it was found that cadmium removal percent increased with an increase in contact time, but removal percent was not evident at 210 min. Therefore the optimum contact time was 180 min for Cd^{2+} ion.

Table 2. Effect of contact time of Cd^{2+} ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Contact time (min)	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ at equilibrium (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
1	30	6.83	31.64
2	60	6.25	37.50
3	90	5.63	43.64
4	120	5.35	46.42
5	150	4.73	52.62
6	180	4.03	59.62
7	210	4.00	59.98

Vol. of Cd^{2+} ion (10 ppm) solution = 20 mL
 $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs = 0.1 g

3.6 Effect of dosage on adsorption of cadmium ion

The adsorption capacities of prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were studied by using model cadmium sulphate solution. Different dosages of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were stirred in 10 ppm model solution for 180 min and determined the final concentration of cadmium using atomic absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Table 3 shows the effect of dosage of Cd^{2+} ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. It can be seen that the maximum cadmium removal percent increased with an increasing dosage

of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles and the best removal percent was found to be 74.20 %.

Table 3. Effect of dosage of Cd^{2+} Ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Weight of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs (g)	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ at equilibrium (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
1	0.1	5.35	46.45
2	0.2	5.26	47.35
3	0.3	4.92	50.79
4	0.4	4.00	59.91
5	0.5	2.57	74.20

Vol. of Cd^{2+} ion (10 ppm) solution = 20 mL
 Time = 180 min

3.7 Removal of cadmium ion in wastewater by using Al_2O_3

In this research, cadmium ion removal in wastewater was carried out with two dosage of Al_2O_3 . It was found that cadmium ion removal percents increased with weight of Al_2O_3 . Table 4 show cadmium removal percents in wastewater by using Al_2O_3 .

Table 4. Cadmium removal percents in wastewater by using Al_2O_3

No.	Weight of Al_2O_3 (g)	Initial $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ (ppm)	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ after removal by Al_2O_3 (ppm)	Removal Percent (%)
1	0.5	3.26	0.97	70.25
2	1.0	3.26	0.12	96.31

Wastewater = 100 mL

Contact time = 180 min

3.8 Removal of cadmium ion in wastewater by using $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

In this research, cadmium ion removal in wastewater was carried out with two dosages of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. It was found that cadmium ion removal percents increased with weight of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. Table 5 shows cadmium removal percents in wastewater by using $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. The higher dosage of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles can remove completely cadmium ion contaminant in wastewater.

Table 5. Cadmium removal percents in wastewater by using $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Weight of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs (g)	Initial $[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ (ppm)	$[\text{Cd}^{2+}]$ after removal by $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs (ppm)	Removal Percent (%)
1	0.5	3.26	0.04	82.40
2	1.0	3.26	0.00	100.00

Wastewater = 100 mL

Contact time = 180 min

3.9 Effect of contact time on adsorption of lead ion

In this research, lead ion removal by $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles using 10 ppm model lead nitrate solution at different contact time. The change of removal percent of cadmium were shown in Table 6. From these observations, it was found that lead ion removal percent increased with an increase in contact time, but removal percent was not evident at 150 to 210 min. Therefore the optimum contact time was 150 min for Pb^{2+} ion.

Table 6. Effect of contact time of Pb^{2+} ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Contact time (min)	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ at equilibrium (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
1	30	0.96	90.37
2	60	0.83	91.67
3	90	0.73	92.64
4	120	0.50	94.99
5	150	0.41	95.90
6	180	0.40	95.92
7	210	0.40	95.94

Vol. of Pb^{2+} ion (10 ppm) solution = 20 mL $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ = 0.1 g

3.10 Effect of dosage on adsorption of lead ion

In the present work, adsorption capacity of prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles was studied by using model lead nitrate solution. Different dosages of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were stirred in 10 ppm model solution for 180 min and determined the final concentration of lead using atomic

absorption spectrophotometer (AAS). Table 7 shows effect of dosage of Pb^{2+} ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles. It can be seen that the maximum lead removal percent increased with an increasing dosage of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles and the best removal percent was found to be 96.91%.

Table 7. Effect of dosage of Pb^{2+} ion removal on $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Weight of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPS (g)	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ at equilibrium (ppm)	Removal percent (%)
1	0.1	0.87	91.28
2	0.2	0.72	92.72
3	0.3	0.57	94.26
4	0.4	0.44	95.58
5	0.5	0.30	96.91

Vol. of Pb^{2+} ion (10 ppm) solution = 20 mL

Time = 150 min

3.11 Lead ion removal in wastewater by using Al_2O_3

In this experiment, lead ion removal in wastewater was carried out with two dosage of active Al_2O_3 . Tables 8 shows lead removal by using Al_2O_3 . It was found that lead removal percents increased with weight of Al_2O_3 .

3.12 Lead ion removal in wastewater by using $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

In this experiment, lead ion removal in wastewater was carried out with two dosages of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. Tables 9 shows lead ion removal percent in wastewater by using Al_2O_3 nanoparticles.

Table 8. Lead removal by using Al_2O_3

No.	Weight of Al_2O_3 (g)	Initial $[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ (ppm)	$[\text{Pb}^{2+}]$ after removal by Al_2O_3 (ppm)	Removal Percent (%)
1	0.5	4.33	2.95	31.79
2	1.0	4.33	1.87	56.81

Wastewater = 100 mL

Contact time = 150 min

It was found that lead ion removal percents increased with weight of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles. The higher dosage of Al_2O_3 nanoparticles can remove completely lead ion contaminant in wastewater.

Table 9. Lead removal percents by using $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles

No.	Weight of $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ NPs (g)	Initial [Pb ²⁺] (ppm)	[Pb ²⁺] after removal by Al_2O_3 NPs (ppm)	Removal Percent (%)
1	0.5	4.33	1.76	98.77
2	1.0	4.33	0.00	100.00

Wastewater = 100 mL
Contact time = 150

4. Conclusion

In this study, aluminium oxide nanoparticles were synthesized by sol-gel assisted auto-combustion method. The prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were characterized by using TG-DTA, XRD, FT-IR and FE-SEM techniques. The resulted $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were used to remove of Cd^{2+} ion and Pb^{2+} ion from modal solution and contaminants in wastewater and was studied the comparison of adsorption properties of the prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles and Al_2O_3 . In this work, the Al_2O_3 and the prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles can be compared removal of Cd^{2+} ion and Pb^{2+} ion under identical conditions, 96.31% of Cd^{2+} ion and 56.81% of Pb^{2+} ion were

removed by one gram Al_2O_3 and the prepared one gram $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles were completely removed Cd^{2+} ion and Pb^{2+} ion contaminants in 100 mL wastewater. The outcome of these researches is that the prepared $\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3$ nanoparticles can be used for heavy metal remediation in wastewater and water treatment for domestic purposes as powerful adsorbents.

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